

A CONCEPT OF RAKTAMAOKSHANA IN NETRAROGA: A REVIEW ARTICLE***¹Dr. Siddhesh Jagdish Patil, ²Dr. Sagar Ghalme, ³Dr. Swati Sarwade**¹PG Scholar, PG 3rd Year, Department of Shalakyatantra, PMT's Ayurved College, Shevgaon (Maharashtra).²Assistant Professor, Department of Shalakyatantra, PMT's Ayurved College, Shevgaon (Maharashtra).³Professor and HOD, Department of Shalakyatantra, PMT's Ayurved College, Shevgaon (Maharashtra).**How to cite this Article:** ¹Dr. Siddhesh Jagdish Patil, ²Dr. Sagar Ghalme, ³Dr. Swati Sarwade (2026). A Concept Of Raktamokshana In Netraroga: A Review Article. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(4), 256–258. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/03/2026

Article Revised on 25/03/2026

Article Published on 04/04/2026

ABSTRACT

Shodhana Karma (purification therapy) plays a vital role not only in providing long-lasting relief but also in disease prevention. It is beneficial in averting conditions such as dermatological disorders, lymph node enlargement, generalised oedema, and haematological diseases, and should be practised periodically. *Netrarogas* (ocular disorders) are classified under *Raktapradoshaja Vikara*, meaning they originate from impure or vitiated blood. The aggravated *Doshas* travel upward through the *Siras* (channels) to the *Urdhvajatru* (region above the clavicle) and lodge in the *Netra* (eyes), leading to the development of eye diseases. *Raktamokshana* (therapeutic bloodletting) is considered the most effective among the *Shodhana* procedures for removing vitiated blood (*Dushita Rakta*). Out of the 76 types of *Netrarogas* described in classical *Ayurvedic* literature, many are recommended for management through *Raktamokshana*. *Jaloukavacharana* (application of leeches) is regarded as the most efficient and appropriate method of *Raktamokshana*, particularly in conditions where *Pitta* is predominantly vitiated in the blood. Among the different modalities of *Raktamokshana*, *Siravyadha* (venesection) and *Jaloukavacharana* hold significant importance in treating ocular disorders.

KEYWORDS: Shodhankarma, Raktamokshana, Siravyadha, Jaloukavacharana.**INTRODUCTION**

Raktamokshana, a para-surgical therapeutic procedure, is increasingly gaining global acceptance and is widely practised today. As described in the *Charaka Samhita*, *Basti Karma* is considered a primary treatment modality, sometimes sufficient on its own. In a similar context, the *Sushruta Samhita* regards *Raktamokshana* as an independent therapeutic modality that can serve as either a complete or a supportive treatment.^[1] It is a key procedure within *Shodhana Karma* and plays a significant role in the management of various ocular disorders. Eye diseases, especially those involving vitiation of *Rakta*, are important in the pathogenesis of *Netraroga*. Such conditions are categorised under *Raktapradoshaja Vikara*. *Raktamokshana* is advocated as an effective line of treatment for these disorders.^[2] The vitiated *Doshas* move upward towards the *Urdhvajatru* region through the *Siras* and, after undergoing *Sthanasamsraya* in the *Netra*, lead to the development of ocular diseases. As mentioned in the *Charaka Samhita*, *Raktamokshana* is especially indicated in *Netraroga* when they are in the stage of *Ragaavastha* (inflammatory

or congestive phase).^[3]**Concept of Raktamokshana**

Raktamokshana is composed of two words- *Rakta*, meaning blood and *Mokshana*, meaning release or elimination. Thus, *Raktamokshana* refers to the process of therapeutic bloodletting.^[4] It is mainly classified into two types.

1. Raktamokshana by Anushastra (non-surgical method)

This type is performed without the use of sharp instruments and includes three procedures.

Jaloukavacharana (leech application): Primarily indicated in the vitiation of *Pitta Dosh*.

Shrungra (bloodletting using a cow's horn): Beneficial in disorders involving *Vata Dosh*.

Alabu (cupping with bottle gourd): Used in conditions associated with *Kapha Dosh*.

2. Raktamokshana by Shastra (surgical method)

This approach involves the use of surgical instruments

and is further divided into two types:

Pracchana: Bloodletting done through multiple small incisions.

Siravyadha: Bloodletting performed by puncturing a vein.

General Contra-indication for *Raktamokshana*

Raktamokshana should be avoided in certain conditions and in specific groups of individuals. It is contraindicated in cases such as *Sarvangashopha* (generalised swelling), *Kshina Pandu* (advanced anaemia), *Garbhini* (pregnancy), *Arsha* (piles), and *Shosha* (severe debility or wasting). It is also not recommended for individuals who have abnormal sweating patterns, such as *Asvinna* (absence of sweating) and *Atisvinna* (excessive sweating), as well as in *Bala* (children), *Vridhdha* (elderly), and *Bhiru* (timid or fearful persons).

Furthermore, it should not be performed in patients suffering from *Dourbalya* (weakness), *Kamala* (jaundice), *Chardi* (vomiting), *Murcha* (syncope), *Pakshaghata* (paralysis), and *Svasa* (breathing disorders). It is also contraindicated in individuals who have recently undergone *Snehapana* (internal oleation) and in those who are *Abhukta* (fasting or on an empty stomach).^[5]

Indication for *Raktamokshana* in *Netraroga*

Raktamokshana is recommended in various ophthalmic conditions. These include *Abhishyanda* (inflammatory disorders of the eye), *Adhimantha* (acute and severe ocular inflammation), *Siraharsha* and *Sirotpata* (vascular disturbances), *Puyalasa* (suppurative eye conditions), and *Vataparyaya* (Vata-related functional abnormalities).

It is also indicated in eyelid disorders such as *Vartmabandha*, *Klishtavartma*, and *Bahalavartma*, as well as in conditions like *Pothaki* and *Anyatovata*. Inflammatory conditions of the eye like *Sashofa Akshipaka* (associated with swelling) and *Ashofa Akshipaka* (without swelling) are also managed with this procedure.

Additionally, it is useful in *Pittaja* and *Kaphaja Timira*, *Savvana Shukla* (ulcerative corneal conditions), *Anjananamika*, and in complications arising from *Arma* (pterygium). *Raktamokshana* is also beneficial in managing *Pilla Rogas*, which involve disorders of the eyelashes.

Raktamokshana kala; *Na Shitakala*, *Natiushna*, *Na Asvinne*, *Natisveda*.

Shrunga and *Alabu*

These techniques are usually performed over areas of the body that are flat, rounded, and adequately fleshy. They are generally not advised in the treatment of *Netraroga* (eye disorders). Classical *Ayurvedic* literature does not describe the use of *Shrunga* and *Alabu* for ocular diseases. However, in practical settings, some *Shalakya*

specialists utilise *Shrunga* at the *Apanga* region (lateral canthus area) for the purpose of *Raktamokshana*.^[6]

Jalaukavacharana

Sushruta has included *Jalauka* (leech therapy) under *Anushastra*, which comprises para-surgical procedures. This therapy is particularly useful in conditions involving vitiated *Rakta*, as it facilitates the removal of impure blood from a localised area of the body.

Among the various *Raktamokshana* techniques, *Jalaukavacharana* is regarded as the most effective due to its simplicity, safety, and greater comfort for the patient, making it a commonly preferred method.^[7]

Types of *Jalouka* – *Savisha* (06) and *Nirvisha* (06).

Acharya Susruta has mentioned that *Jalouka* (Leech) sucks impure blood from affected site & reduces symptoms like burning sensation, pain, swelling, redness etc.^[8]

Indication of *Jaloukavacharana*

Abhishyanda, *Adhimantha*, *Anjananamika*, *Siraharsha*, *Sirotpata*, *Puyalasa*, *Vatparyaya*, *Anyatovata*, *Sashofa Akshipaka*, *Ashofa Akshipaka*.

Avgadha-Grathita-pitta Dushita Rakta.

METHOD: *Jaloukavacharana* should be done as per the classical method.

Pracchana

A tourniquet is applied above the selected site to promote dilation of the blood vessels. Subsequently, superficial incisions are made using a sharp instrument, taking care to avoid damage to important structures such as *Marma* (vital points), *Snayu* (ligaments/tendons), *Sandhi* (joints), *Asthi* (bones), and *Sira* (blood vessels).

Indication

Vartmavbandha, *Klishtavartma*, *Bahalavartma*, *Pothaki*. *Pindita Rakta*.

METHOD

Ruju- straight

Nati Uttana- not too superficial

Na Tiryaka- not obliquely *Nati Gambhira*- not too deep

Asankirna - not very near.

Siravyadha

Siravyadha is regarded as a powerful therapeutic procedure that eradicates diseases from their origin, much like crops in a field dry up completely when the water supply is cut off.^[9]

Sites for *Siravyadha*

The procedure is commonly performed at *Lalata* (forehead), *Apanga* (outer canthus), and *Upanasa* (inner canthus).

Appropriate Time (Kala)^[10]

In *Varsha Rutu* (rainy season), on non-cloudy days.

In *Ushna Rutu* (summer season), during cooler times of the day
In *Shita Rutu* (winter season), during relatively warmer periods.

Size of the Puncture

In fleshy (muscular) regions: equivalent to the size of a *Yava* (barley grain) In other areas: *Ardha Yava* (half barley grain) or one *Brihi* (rice grain)

Over bony surfaces: *Ardha Yava* (half barley grain)

Indications

Conditions such as *Puyalasa*, *Savrana Shukla*, and complications of *Arma Pittaja Timira* and *Kaphaja Timira*

All varieties of *Abhishyanda*

Pilla Roga, *Adhimantha*, and *Pothaki*

Generalised *Rakta Dushti* affecting the whole body.

DISCUSSION

Netrarogas are classified under *Raktapradoshaja Vikara* (diseases caused by vitiated blood), hence *Raktamokshana* (bloodletting therapy) is considered highly useful in their treatment. *Acharya Sushruta* has mentioned that disorders arising from vitiated blood, when managed with *Raktamokshana*, show minimal chances of recurrence (*Apunarbhava*). Before selecting a suitable method of *Raktamokshana*, the state and involvement of *Rakta* should be properly evaluated. Techniques like *Shrungra* and *Alabu* are generally not indicated in eye diseases. *Jalouka* (leech therapy) is especially beneficial in conditions where the *doshas* are clotted (*Grathita*) or deeply seated (*Avagadha*), as it helps in removing impure blood from the affected region. Disorders such as *Utsangini* and *Anjananamika* can be effectively treated with *Jaloukavacharana*. *Siravyadha* (venesection) is particularly indicated in *Netrarogas* associated with discharge (*Strava*) and pain (*Vedana*), such as *Abhishyanda*, *Adhimantha*, and *Timira*. *Prachhanna* (scarification) improves local circulation in cases of localised accumulation of vitiated blood (*Pindita Rakta*) and aids in its elimination. It is beneficial in conditions like *Pothaki* and is also advised as a preparatory step before performing *Lekhana Karma*.

CONCLUSION

Raktamokshana is regarded as a highly effective line of management for *Raktapradoshaja Netraroga* (ocular disorders due to vitiated blood). *Jaloukavacharana* (leech therapy) is especially indicated in conditions with *Grathita Rakta* (localized or clotted vitiated blood), particularly in *Vartmagata Roga* (diseases of the eyelids). When the vitiated *Doshas* spread throughout the entire eye, *Siravyadha* (venesection) is considered the appropriate treatment approach.

REFERENCES

1. Priyavat Sharma, Charaka Samhita; Sri Agniveshakrita; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan,

- Varanasi. Reprint 2008 Sidhdisthana 1/40-42.
2. Dr. Bramhanand Tripathi, Ashtang Hridayam of Srimadavagbhata edited with Nirmala Hindi commentary, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, Reprint 2013. Sutrasthana 27/5.
3. Priyavat Sharma, Charaka Samhita; Sri Agniveshakrita; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Varanasi. Reprint 2008 Sutrasthana 24/11.
4. Kaviraj Ambikadatta Sashtri, Susrutasamhita edited with 'Ayurvedatatvasandipika' Hindi commentary; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Varanasi, Reprint 2012 Sutrasthana 14/25.
5. Dr. Bramhanand Tripathi, Ashtang Hridayam of Srimadavagbhata edited with Nirmala Hindi commentary, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, Reprint 2013. Sutrasthana 27/3-5.
6. Kaviraj Ambikadatta Sashtri, Susruta Samhita edited with 'Ayurvedatatvasandipika' Hindi commentary; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Varanasi, Reprint, 2012.
7. Sharirasthana 8/25-26.
8. Dr. Bramhanand Tripathi, Ashtang Hridayam of Srimadavagbhata edited with Nirmala Hindi commentary, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, Reprint 2013. Sutrasthana 26/53-55.
9. Kaviraj Ambikadatta Sashtri, Susruta Samhita edited with 'Ayurvedatatvasandipika' Hindi commentary; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Varanasi, Reprint 2012 Sutrasthana 13/3.
10. Dr. Bramhanand Tripathi, Ashtang Hridayam of Srimadavagbhata edited with Nirmala Hindi commentary, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, Reprint 2013. Sutrasthana 26/53-54.
11. Kaviraj Ambikadatta Sashtri, Susruta Samhita edited with 'Ayurvedatatvasandipika' Hindi commentary; Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Varanasi, Reprint 2012 Sharirasthana 8/17.